

MODELING OF DEFORMATION AT FLOW-CONTACTING ELEMENTS OF ENERGY-SAVING WATER LIFTING INSTALLATION

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Abstract. This article discusses the methods of calculation of vortex spillways with chamberless tangential swirlers of various geometric shapes, the study of features of transformation of the swirling flow in their flowing parts and the identification of regularities of the influence of the interaction of rotating and axial flows on the hydraulic conditions of the structure, allowing to choose the optimal modes of operation of such culverts and the designation of their structural elements.

Keywords: cavitation, Fluid flow, Turbulence, Vibrations, Reservoir outlets, Hydroelectric facilities, Water flow dynamics, Channel design, Flow modeling.

Statement of the question. Many issues of energy-saving water lifting installation in the Republic of Uzbekistan, caused by problems of economic, ecological and social character, requires solving complex problems of creation of deep water lifting installations capable of reliable operation at sufficient suction heads rising more than 100 m and flow velocities up to 50...60 m/s. At noted values of determining parameters of the latter it is necessary to: reliably protect the flowing part of spillways from cavitation erosion; reduce dynamic loads on elements of water lifting installation; prevent the possibility of significant damages of fixing and inadmissible bottom scouring.

Pic.1. Vortex shaft spillway.

a-vertical section; b-plan; 1- underwater canal; 2- spiral chamber; 3-vertical chamber; 4-deflector; 5- diversion tunnel; 6-free water surface level curve along the spiral chamber walls.

One of the areas of technology where the widest application of swirling water flows is possible is water lifting technology. Water lifting hydraulic structures, usually utilizing the positive effects arising from the swirling of water flow, have long attracted the attention of specialists, especially in the design of high-pressure water lifting plants.

Pic.2. Vibration at the Karkidon Reservoir outfall bends with constant depth.

In place of water lifting plants and interestingly the operation of spillway structures, particularly interesting is the operation of vortex spillways with swirling flow, which have been called vortex spillways.

To date, certain experience has been accumulated in the design of spillways with twisting flow in tunnels and conduits of Rezaksai, Karkidon and other reservoirs. In this case, it usually provided intensive damping of excess kinetic energy and simultaneously created increased pressure on the walls of the conduit, which allows for properly [1,2,5] designed structure to reduce or eliminate the danger of cavitation when flowing contacting with the flow of surfaces and structural elements of the latter. Effective damping of flow energy inside the tunnel and damping chamber, in case of its application, allows to reduce the water velocity at the outlet of the spillway to acceptable values, which in turn simplifies the design of structures for concentrated energy damping at the end section of the spillway.

Vibrations at the turns of the Karkidon reservoir outlets with constant depth occur sometimes after the onset of cavitation, in which the fluid flow detaches from the solid boundary of the streamlined body or channel wall with the formation of a cavity, or cavern, on the solid boundary. The immobile, or attached, cavern is stable, only in the quasi-stationary sense. Its boundary sometimes looks like the surface of an intensely boiling turbulized liquid. In other the interface between the fluid and the large cavern may be smooth and transparent. Vortex cavitation in fluid flow is observed at the center of vortices, cavitation formed in areas where there are large tangential stresses.

There is no significant difference between cavitation in a fluid flow and cavitation on a body moving in a stationary fluid. In both cases, the important parameters are relative velocities and pressures. The only difference worth mentioning is the lower level of turbulence in the still

fluid. Cavitation in fluid flow is often observed in relatively long channels in which turbulence is fully developed to the cavitation zone [1,3,6].

In this case, the tangent of the bottom slope angle in the transverse direction is equal to

$$k = \frac{dz_{\partial h}}{dr} \quad (1)$$

From equation (4) when

$$kdr = dz_{\partial h}$$

we get;

$$\frac{dh}{dr} = \frac{2\left(H_0 - h - \frac{dz_{\partial h}}{dr}\right)}{r} - \frac{dz_{\partial h}}{dr} \quad (2)$$

And at $h = \text{const}$, hence $\frac{dh}{dr} = 0$, the equality (5), i.e. the depth at change of the bottom radius at rotation has the form:

$$\frac{dz_{\partial h}}{dr} = \frac{2(H_0 - h)}{3r} \quad (3)$$

After integration:

$$\frac{z_{\partial h}}{H_0 - h} = \frac{2}{3} \ln r + \ln C \quad (4)$$

Having defined C from the condition, that at

$$z_{\partial h} = z_0, r = r_0,$$

We get:

$$z_{\partial h} - z_0 = \frac{2}{3}(H_0 - h) \ln \frac{r}{r_0} \quad (5)$$

At $z_0 = 0$

$$z_{\partial h} = \frac{2}{3}(H_0 - h) \ln \frac{r}{r_0} \quad (6)$$

The formation of transverse waves leading to vortex motion on the rotation of a turbulent flow along the arc of a circle. When a turbulent flow in a channel of rectangular cross-section turns along the arc of a circle, the perturbation arising at the points and propagates along the straight lines AB and $A'B$, and beyond the point B - along the curves VM and VM' . At the outer wall, between points A and M , the water level rises, at the inner wall, between A' and M' , falls. [4,5,6] (pic.2.) Further, the increase and decrease of the free surface level at the walls alternate; wave reflection occurs at points M and M' and at subsequent points where waves meet the walls. If we assume that the velocity in the cross section is constant, which is close to reality due to the influence of friction forces, and the points M and M' lie on the same straight line OS , then from geometric considerations

$$AC = \frac{b}{\operatorname{tg} \alpha} \operatorname{tg} \theta = \frac{AC}{\frac{b}{2} + r_0}$$

from where

$$\theta = \arctg \frac{2b}{(2r_0 + b)tg\alpha} \quad (7)$$

Where α - calculated by the formula (5). Found angle θ corresponds to half a wavelength, traceable at walls. Subsequent maxima at the outer wall and minima at the inner wall will appear after $3\theta, 5\theta$ etc.

The formula for determining the rise and fall of the free surface level at the walls can be derived from the equation of change in the quantity of motion when the flow is rotated by the angle θ by integrating it within 0° to θ . More simply, the formula is obtained from the equilibrium condition of the flow in the cross section. Consider the cross-section $M-M'$ (we have the first maximum on the outer wall at the point M). Determining the normal acceleration along the mean radius, we obtain:

$$h_2 - h_1 = \frac{g^2 b}{r_0 g} \quad (8)$$

where h_1 and h_2 — depths at the inner and outer walls, respectively. Due to the small dissipation of energy along the length of the rotation, the amplitude of oscillations, levels can be assumed constant, i.e. equal, the wavelength is

$$2AC \approx 2AC' = \frac{2b}{tg\alpha}.$$

In order to prevent disturbances from penetrating the straight channel beyond the bend, the curvilinear section should be limited to sections $2\theta, 4\theta$ etc., where the water level is horizontal. Pairing of turnouts with rectangular channel segments. In the water-conducting nodes of reservoirs, disturbance waves propagating along the length of the channel are generated in the initial cross-section of the bend. The smaller is the radius of rotation, the greater is the height of the free surface perturbation waves, which can be seen from the formula (8). The turning section may interface with the inlet and outlet sections in a variety of ways. Over the entire length of the turn, the radius can be made decreasing from $r \rightarrow \infty$ up to some value (rectilinear section) and then back to the $r \rightarrow \infty$. At some length of rotation its curvature can be constant (pic.2). The axis of the fast-current turning radius can be delineated, for example, by a curve [3,7] (pic.2.)

$$y = a_0 \cos \frac{\pi x}{2x_0} \quad (9)$$

where a_0 - permanent, its value is determined from the condition

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = tg \frac{\alpha}{2} \quad (10)$$

to be carried out at the ends of the turning section:

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = -\frac{\pi a_0}{2x_0} \sin \frac{\pi x}{2x_0}$$

At

$$x = x_0 \sin \frac{\pi x}{2 x_0} = 1 \quad (11)$$

It is known that the radius of curvature is determined by the expression

$$R = \frac{\left[1 + \left(\frac{dy}{dx} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\frac{d^2 y}{dx^2}}$$

Calculated and experimental data are given in feet, and feet per second, 1-by experiments; 2-by calculation.

$$R_{s1} = \infty \quad R_{s2} = 160 \quad R_{s3} = 68,90 \\ R_{s4} = 40,24 \quad R_{s5} = 28,21 \quad R_{s6} = 24,69$$

In our case:

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \operatorname{tg} \frac{\alpha}{2} \sin \frac{\pi x}{2 x_0} \\ \frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} = \frac{\pi}{2 x_0} \operatorname{tg} \frac{\alpha}{2} \cos \frac{\pi x}{2 x_0}$$

Consequently, for the fast-flow axis, the radius of curvature at rotation is determined by the following formula:

$$R_s = \frac{\left[1 + \left(\operatorname{tg} \frac{\alpha}{2} \sin \frac{\pi x}{2 x_0} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\frac{\pi}{2 x_0} \operatorname{tg} \frac{\alpha}{2} \cos \frac{\pi x}{2 x_0}} \quad (12)$$

Where $\frac{\pi}{2 x_0} \operatorname{tg} \frac{\alpha}{2}$ - for a given fast flow is a constant value. The conjugate section, giving a quieter free surface.

Conclusion:

The analysis of operation of high-pressure spillways at a number of hydroelectric complexes has shown that in many cases the rational layout of structures of the latter depends on how well the spillway structures are placed in its structure.

Design and construction of hydroelectric facilities with water heads up to 200 m and more posed a number of problems, among which special importance belongs to the problems of cavitation and dynamic impact of the flow on the elements of the flowing part of the structure, conjugation in plan and height of the spillway tract sections, as well as damping of excessive flow energy in the downstream.

The most widespread vortex spillways are designs of this type favorably differ from conventional spillways by the stability of mine operation at changing flow rates. Their advantages also include: the possibility of a sharp change in the direction of forward motion at the twist node;

reduction of the danger of cavitation erosion of the tunnel lining due to the action of centrifugal forces; more intensive damping of excessive flow energy along the length compared to axial flow, which significantly improves the conditions of flow exit to the downstream.

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